

BIOMIMICRY OF PLANTAE VASCULES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-HEALING COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

This paper presents the first investigation into the concept of creating a *Plantae* inspired vascular network within a fibre reinforced polymer composite laminate which provides an ongoing self-healing functionality but does not incur a mass penalty. Through the application of a 'lost-wax' technique, parallel hollow vasculae, similar to 'ray cells' in ring porous hardwoods, were successfully introduced within a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy polymer composite laminate. The influence of single and dual vasculae on the surrounding composite fibre architecture (i.e. introduction of fibre waviness and resin rich pockets) was characterised experimentally using a compression-after-impact test methodology. It has been shown that the vasculae interact with the impact damage but they do not promote a preferential failure path whether aligned parallel or normal to the host plies. The compressive failure strength was found to be comparable in the baseline orientation and parallel (0°) configurations for both the undamaged and damaged (10J) cases. In the case of the normal (90°) vasculae the formation of resin rich pockets does not appear to have degraded the relative compressive performance of the laminate, although intuitively the out-of-plane ply variation would be expected to trigger the early onset of compression failure. The interlaminar tensile strength tests illustrated that although a knockdown in performance occurs as a result of the vasculae inclusion (39% for the 90-degree vasculae, 43% for the 45-degree vasculae and 61% for the inclusion of the aligned vasculae), the off-axis vasculae (and their associated resin-rich pockets) perform better than the vasculae aligned to their host ply. This observation may explain the difference in performance observed in the compression tests where the aligned vasculae not damaged by the impact event, but in close proximity to the damage site, help alter the stress state ahead of the crack thus initiating earlier failure. In conclusion, the research undertaken here illustrates the positive and negative influences the vasculae have on the global compressive failure mode as a minimum-mass self-healing solution. Following this new understanding, better bioinspired composite materials can be designed which harness the inherent damage tolerant capabilities to 'direct' a propagating crack into a predetermined healing feature.

KEYWORDS:

self-repair, biomimetic, impact damage, vascular network, compression, damage tolerance

1. INTRODUCTION

In a materials engineering context, the concept of self-healing is applicable where manufacturing or operationally induced damage can be repaired by the materials already entrained within the structure, i.e. self-healing of engineering structures should be analogous to the healing process of living organisms whether from the *Animalia* and *Plantae* biological kingdoms (Trask *et al.* 2007a). In recent years, research groups have developed discrete bioinspired concepts for autonomous delivery of a mobile fluid phase from either microcapsules, (e.g. Kessler & White 2001; White *et al.* 2001), or hollow fibres, (e.g. Pang & Bond 2005; Trask and Bond 2006; Trask *et al.* 2007b, Bond *et al.* 2008) to effect repair of bulk polymeric and advanced fibre reinforced polymer composite materials. This concept has taken a further biomimetic step with the introduction of integrated, pervasive vascular networks at the micro and meso-scale (e.g. Toohey *et al.* 2007; Williams *et al.* 2007), which have been demonstrated to provide a replenishable and repeated self-healing function.

In bulk polymeric materials, the inclusion of microcapsules or vascular networks has been found to have negligible detrimental effect on the material's structure and performance, as the polymer is able to form around and easily accommodate any added self-healing entities. The situation for advanced fibre reinforced polymer composite materials is more complex as they comprise at least two distinct phases: a reinforcement, typically a fibre (carbon, glass or aramid) of 10 μ m to 30 μ m in diameter oriented in a 2D plane according to the anticipated loading environment; and a polymer matrix material (e.g. polyester, epoxy, or cyanate-ester) which fully envelopes the reinforcement. The inclusion of discrete self-healing entities, whether hollow glass fibres, microcapsules or a vascular network, can easily disrupt the composite architecture (i.e. in-plane and out-of-plane fibre alignment) resulting in a detrimental effect on mechanical performance. Furthermore, poorly designed vascular networks have been shown to potentially incur a significant mass penalty (values up to 25% have been reported by Williams *et al.* (2007)). To overcome, or at least minimise the disruption to the host material by inclusion of a self-healing system, one obvious approach is to seek minimisation of system dimensions, e.g. nano-capsules (Blaiszik *et al.* (2008)). However, the application of nano-capsules restricts the available healing potential to tackle only very minor damage states, unless the volume loading is increased to such an extent that it again affects the inherent properties of the host material/structure.

An alternative solution is the design and formation of a carefully designed integrated self-healing vascular network system that takes much bioinspiration from the numerous proven approaches in the *Animalia* and *Plantae* biological kingdoms (Williams *et al.* (2007); (2008a)). These two groups of organisms offer distinct sources of inspiration for the development of self-healing capabilities within synthetic fibrous polymer composite materials. Whilst both groups generally incorporate a capability to transport fluid around a structure using 'vascular networks', their configurations and detailed designs are divergent (with some notable exceptions e.g. leaves).

McCulloh and colleagues have published several papers (McCulloh *et al.* 2003; 2004; McCulloh & Sperry 2005) which discuss possible reasons for these different approaches in Nature, and the applicability of Murray's law (Murray, 1926) which helps derive rules for network design. In *Plantae* organisms, the nutrient carrying longitudinal cells which transport nutrients from the roots to canopy tend to run parallel to one another without intersecting. Conversely, *Animalia* tend to have branching vascular networks

which carry fluids around the organism. This network is a hierarchical design with larger supply channels (veins and arteries) breaking down into progressively smaller vesicles (capillaries) at various points around the animal's body.

In this study, the inspiration of integrating a healing functionality in composite laminates stems from hardwood morphology and the interaction of the impact resistance and energy-absorbing characteristics of their internal features on their performance under compressive loading (Reiterer *et al.* (2002), Stanzl-Tschegg (2006) and Hepworth *et al.* (2002).

Figure 1: (a) Ray cells in ash hardwood, (b) Scanning Electron Microscopy of the fracture surface in ash on the radial-longitudinal plane. (Reiterer *et al.* 2002).

The studies by Reiterer *et al.* (2002) and Stanzl-Tschegg (2006) considered the role of ray cells in the radial direction in both oak and ash hardwood trees. Figure 1 illustrates the fracture plane of a ring porous hardwood, ash (Reiterer *et al.* 2002). In hardwood morphologies the role of the ray cells is to transport nutrients across the diameter of the tree. In Figure 1 (a) and (b), the longitudinal load bearing fibres are seen to flow around the ray cells with minimal disruption. By investigating two generally similar wood structures with different ray cell characteristics, Reiterer *et al.* (2002) and Stanzl-Tschegg (2006) reported the influence of these features on the tensile strength and fracture mechanics performance in the radial reinforcement of the ring porous hardwood structure. Reiterer *et al.* (2002) concluded that the ray cells act as stiff pins preventing the layers of different stiffness (i.e. earlywood and latewood) from slipping past each other.

This paper describes the first investigation into the concept of forming and integrating a bioinspired vascular network based healing function within a fibre reinforced polymer composite laminate which does not incur a mass penalty. In essence, the aim of this research is to form an integral network in a host material during fabrication without compromising the overall performance, an approach commonly observed in *Plantae*. For example, at the macroscopic level, spruce wood can be considered a cellular solid, comprised of parallel hollow tubes in the cell walls. Whilst the internal features in wood are distinctly different to fibre reinforced polymeric composite materials, the development of a synthetic material that mimics the vessel morphology of hardwoods are critical for minimum mass composite structures. Although direct biomimicry of the complex design of a hardwood is beyond current capabilities in advanced fibre reinforced composite materials, it is the concept of integrating vasculature within a structural material without incurring additional mass, and understanding the consequences on damage initiation that is under consideration in this work.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The overall objective of this research activity is to assess the feasibility of introducing a bio-inspired self-healing vascular network into a fibre reinforced polymer composite, based on design principles observed in *Plantae*. Critically, such an introduction must result in limited disruption to the surrounding structural fibre architecture (and hence the mechanical properties). The self-healing agent to be transported through such a system has not been investigated as part of this study. This will form the basis for future studies.

At various locations in a segregated, branched or grid network within a composite laminate, the vascular network will be misaligned with the local reinforcing fibres. The control of this misalignment is paramount in ensuring that the influence on the structural performance of resin pockets and fibre distortions is minimised.

To begin to understand the feasibility and consequences of incorporating such vascular networks, a series of experimental trials have been undertaken. The first concerns methods by which such features can be readily fabricated within a composite laminate. Once this was established, the research was structured to assess the influence of such an embedded network running parallel and perpendicular to the local structural reinforcing fibres, to quantify the likely disruption on (1) interlaminar tensile strength and (2) the impact and compressive strength response of the host material. This approach ensured a fundamental understanding of vascular deployment within a laminated composite material.

3. FABRICATING A VASCULAR NETWORK IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

The initial phase of the work sought to develop a means by which a simple vascular network could be formed in-situ within a typical laminated fibre reinforced polymer composite. The material selected for this study was an aerospace grade carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Hexcel Composites IM7/8552) unidirectional prepregged tape with a nominal ply thickness of 0.127 mm. The panel dimensions were 200mm x 150mm. The balanced and symmetric stacking sequence, with the position of the vasculae included within the lay-up scheme, has been shown schematically illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the vasculae location in the $[0/45/90/-45/0_2/45/90/-45/0]_s$ stacking sequence.

The selection of the fibre stacking sequence for the dual vasculae network was governed by the need for a relatively large vasculae diameter (0.25mm) and the desire to introduce the vasculae at approximately quarter and three-quarter positions through the laminate thickness. Hence the laminate ply stacking sequence selected was 18 plies arranged as

[0/45/90/-45/0₂/45/90/-45//-45/90/45/0₂/-45/90/45/0] with the vasculures residing between the paired 0° plies located at the fifth and twelfth ply locations (underscored). In this laminate two additional 0° plies are included to accommodate the vasculures.

The vasculures were formed by a ‘lost-wax’ type process using low melting temperature (LMT) wire (0.25mm diameter, Sn 60%, Pb 40% Solder Chemistry, Landshut, Germany) positioned at key interfaces between plies to form parallel channels within the laminated composite before autoclave processing. The LMT wire was aligned at either 0°, 45° or 90° to the adjacent plies within a laminate (as indicated in Figure 3). The LMT wire was selected such that it would survive exposure to the manufacturer’s recommended cure cycle for the composite resin system, namely 120 °C for 1 hr, followed by 180 °C for 2 hr, with a temperature ramp rate of 2°C per minute and a pressure of 700 kPa. The LMT was subsequently removed under the application of a post-cure process of 190°C for 2 hours whilst held under vacuum. Once removed an open channel or vasculure, as shown in Figure 3, was created.

Figure 3: Composite laminate with stacking sequence $[(-45,90,+45,0)_2]_s$ with LMT wire network aligned at (a) 90° to the adjacent 0° plies, (b) 45° to the adjacent 0° plies, and (c) parallel to the adjacent 0° plies

Figure 3 illustrates the typical level of disruption resulting from the wire inclusion at three different ply interface locations. As expected, when the LMT wire is misaligned with the surrounding fibres a resin rich pocket is formed (Figures 3a & 3b), a feature absent from ring porous hardwoods where the ray cells nest comfortably amongst the longitudinal reinforcing ‘fibres’ (Figure 1). The overall length of the resin pocket created depends upon the angular mismatch between the vasculure and the local reinforcing fibres, and the conformability of the fibres during processing. For example, a 45° fibre can be more readily formed around a LMT wire preform than a fibre at 90° due to the difference in their relative stiffness. In these experiments, the host ply vertical deformation relative to horizontal ply, was recorded at 7.5 degrees with a slight variation arising from the LMT wire undergoing some softening during exposure to 180°C and being deformed under the 700kPa pressure. In the aligned case (Figure 3c), the local reinforcing fibres and the vasculure embed very well with only slight fibre waviness in the adjacent plies.

As detailed in section 2, the aim of this investigation is to introduce a healing storage reservoir without incurring a mass penalty. This has clearly been successful, however,

as Figure 4(a) and 4(b) clearly indicate, a resin rich pocket has formed around the vascule even though the manufacturing method is a closed system, i.e. no additional resin has been introduced to the laminate. To accommodate the formation of the localised resin rich pocket, resin must be redistributed from the surrounding local area, i.e. the local plies. This is evident in both Figure 3(a) and 3(b) where a localised increase in fibre volume fraction occurs above the vascule (identified as ‘A’ in Figure 3(a) & (b)) and the formation of internal porosity (identified as ‘B’ in Figure 3(a) & (b)) at the run-out of the resin rich pocket. The implication of these three features, a resin rich pocket, regions of higher volume fraction and porosity, on the initiation and propagation of the compressive failure mode is uncertain. When the vascule is aligned with the host ply (Figure 3(c)), no resin rich pocket is created which eliminates the formation of any internal porosity. However, the fibres in the host ply still need to accommodate the LMT wire, which once again results in a local volume fraction variation around the vascule, point A in Figure 3(c).

In an effort to understand the influence of this localised variation on the failure sequence, a series of interlaminar tensile strength tests were undertaken in the first instance.

4. VASCULE INFLUENCE ON INTERLAMINAR TENSILE STRENGTH

The influence of the vascules on the interlaminar tensile strength was undertaken by assessing the failure initiation arising from out-of-plane stresses in the hump back bridge specimen (HBB). In this study a series of controlled tests were carried out on carbon fibre-epoxy curved beams loaded in four-point bending using the loading conditions shown in Figure 4. The specimen was manufactured from 32 plies of IM7-8552 carbon epoxy unidirectional tape with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm. They were sectioned in to 10mm wide and positioned on 10mm diameter loading rollers with the loading rate set to 2mm/min.

Figure 4: Schematic of the loading and support points.

Although no test standard exists, the hump-back bridge specimens have been assessed at the University of Bristol in the past indicating that this test geometry can provide a robust method for assessing the interlaminar tensile strength of composite materials. In terms of data analysis, the same data processing scheme recommended in the ASTM D 6415-99 was employed. The HBB results were processed with the formula recommended in the ASTM D 6415-99 standard originally due to the theory proposed by Lekhnitskii [Lekhnitskii et al, 1968] for stresses in a cylindrical anisotropic homogeneous curved beam under pure bending.

The interlaminar tensile strength results for the baseline material and the three different vascule orientations (parallel, 45-degrees, and normal to the host plies) is presented in

Figure 5. Representative failure modes for the different samples has also been included for completeness.

Figure 5: Influence of vasculer orientation on ILTS

The results in Figure 5 indicate that the inclusion of a vasculer gallery, whether aligned or misaligned to the host ply, reduces the interlaminar tensile strength of the baseline specimen (122MPa, CV 9%) by 39% for the inclusion of the 90-degree vasculer (75MPa, CV 8%), by 43% for the 45-degree vasculer (69MPa, CV 6%) and by 61% for the inclusion of the aligned vasculer. The comparatively low result for the aligned vasculers compared to the vasculers normal and at 45-degrees to the host ply may be attributed to the toughening effect arising from the formation of the 8552 resin rich pocket around the vasculer. Whilst initially considering these open galleries as sources of damage initiation it appears the increased volume of resin may have protected the vasculer from the onset of failure. However, the formation of these pockets was observed to alter the localised volume fraction around the gallery and introduce regions of porosity above and outside the end of the ‘pocket’ tip. It was these regions which appeared to initiate failure, although this point is still under investigation because cracking was observed to remain remote from the vasculer and penetrate the vasculer within the same vasculer batch. Conversely, in the case of the aligned vasculer, the resin rich pocket does not exist and the stress concentration arising from these open holes has clearly triggered failure (see insert picture of Figure 5).

5. DAMAGE INTERACTION WITH VASCULAR NETWORK.

In an effort to determine the magnitude and extent of damage interaction with the vascular network, an Instron Dynatup drop weight tower was used to assess the two different laminate configurations, namely (1) single vasculer network at the centreline of the specimen or (2) dual vasculer network symmetrically arranged about the centreline. The vasculer was positioned such that it was either aligned or normal to the host ply, i.e. 0-degrees or 90-degrees. The specimens were then subjected to a series of 10J

impacts and assessed using Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) ultrasonic C-scan apparatus before being tested in compression.

The NDE C-scan for the single and the dual vascule laminates yielded very similar results. Notably, the inclusion of the vascular network was not observed to increase the expected area of the damage site. It was thought that the network might ‘promote’ additional local damage growth, i.e. the formation of a classical ‘spiral staircase’ of damage at ply interfaces through the specimen thickness would manifest itself as a greater ‘step’ area per interface. However, this was not observed to be the case for either configuration. This point has been illustrated in Figure 6, which details the damage formation after a 10J impact within the dual network laminate, i.e. $[0/45/90/-45/\underline{0}_2/45/90/-45// -45/90/45/\underline{0}_2/-45/90/45/0]$. The figure includes the scans from the baseline material without any internal network, the vascule spaced 5mm apart and positioned parallel (0°) and normal (90°) to the host ply. The white vertical and black horizontal lines visible in the images are the ultrasonic reflection from the vascules.

Figure 6: NDE of $[0/45/90/-45/\underline{0}_2/45/90/-45// -45/90/45/\underline{0}_2/-45/90/45/0]$: C-scan image of three different specimen configurations after 10J impact (a) no network, (b) 5mm network spacing aligned parallel (0°) to host ply, (c) 10mm vascule aligned normal (90°) to host ply. The presence of the vascular network is visible in each sample as either vertical white or horizontal dark lines.

4. COMPRESSION STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT DAMAGE

To investigate the effect of relative alignment of the vascules and surrounding host plies and the consequences for the mechanical performance of the composite laminate, a series of compression strength measurements were made following low velocity impact testing. A specimen of dimensions 89 mm x 55 mm was machined from the impacted panel insuring the impact event was located centrally. The compression testing was conducted on an Instron 1342 test machine using a 250kN load cell. The sample was placed inside an anti-buckling fixture designed specifically for compression testing of composite laminates (in accordance with ASTM D7137). The compressive loading was applied under displacement control at a rate of 0.4mm/min until failure occurred. The compressive strength test results for the dual network laminate ($[0/45/90/-45/\underline{0}_2/45/90/-45// -45/90/45/\underline{0}_2/-45/90/45/0]$) are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: CAI results for the [0/45/90/-45/0₂/45/90/-45// -45/90/45/0₂/-45/90/45/0] laminate with the dual network parallel or normal to the host plies.

Specimen designation	CAI _{Average} (MPa)	Stdev	Failure mode	Normalised
Laminate (no network, no impact)	351	28	End crushing	1.00
0-degree vasculature, no impact	339	23	End crushing	0.97
90-degree vasculature, no impact	374	10	End crushing	1.07
Laminate (no network, 10J impact)	281	28	Central crushing	0.80
0-degree vasculature, 10J Impact	286	27	Central crushing	0.82
90-degree vasculature, 10J impact	296	8	Central crushing	0.84

As Table 4.1 indicates, the three non-impacted configurations all failed by end brooming along the load introduction face. The impact damaged samples all failed with comparable strengths with central buckling of the damage site. This illustrates that although the inclusion of the 90-degree network generates localised resin rich pockets and disruption of the surrounding plies it does not appear to have influenced the compressive failure strength. In the context of the ILTS results, it is hypothesised that the formation of the resin rich pockets ‘protect’ the vasculature from the onset of damage initiation when the sample is loaded in a global state of compression. Although locally a state of transverse tension exists through the laminate about the vasculatures. Further work is ongoing to clarify this observation.

5. DISCUSSION

In the case of the dual vascular network positioned at quarter and three-quarter positions through the thickness of the [0/45/90/-45/0₂/45/90/-45// -45/90/45/0₂/-45/90/45/0] composite lay-up, the compressive failure strength is comparable in the baseline orientation and parallel (0°) configurations for both the undamaged and damaged cases. In the case of the normal (90°) vasculature the formation of resin rich pockets does not appear to have degraded the compressive performance of the laminate, although intuitively the out-of-plane ply variation would be expected to trigger the onset of compression failure. The interlaminar tensile strength tests illustrated that although a knockdown in performance occurs as a result of the vasculatures inclusion, the off-axis vasculature (and their associated resin-rich pockets) perform better than the vasculatures aligned to their host ply. This observation may explain the difference in performance observed in the compression tests.

Control of the resin pockets is a critical consideration for the self-healing concept. For example, in *Plantae* the ‘reinforcing fibres’ are aligned and orientated around open channels to ensure maximum load carrying capability. Current composites manufacturing capability is able to tailor fibres in either a horizontal or vertical plane but not both simultaneously, as observed in natural composite structures. Such a capability would lead to the absence of the resin rich pocket surrounding an open channel. Providing that a three-dimensional architecture could be developed to ensure the attraction of a propagating crack front rather than deflecting it away, then biomimicry of vascular designs found in plant structures could be used to satisfy the

minimum mass requirements of a healing agent vascular transportation network within a composite structure.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This is the first study to show that a simple bioinspired vascular network can be integrated within an advanced fibre reinforced polymer composite material with no mass increase and minimal detrimental effect on the local or global mechanical performance of the material. The approach of using the matrix material within a fibre reinforced polymer composite to form an integral vascular network in-situ has been shown to be effective. In comparison to the effect of such features in hardwood morphologies on mechanical properties, similar attributes such as impact energy absorption have been conferred. Whilst considerable research in this nascent field remains, biomimicry of such integrated natural features whether for self-healing or integration of structural health monitoring appears to be a viable option for advanced fibre reinforced polymer composites.

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